

Research Article

Growth Performance and Comparison of Cowpea Varieties under Different NaCl Salinity Stresses

*Fazal Hadi¹, Farrukh Hussain¹ and Muhammad Arif²

¹Centre of Plant Biodiversity/Botanical Garden, University of Peshawar, Pakistan,

²Department of Agronomy, KPK Agricultural University, Peshawar, Pakistan

*Corresponding author's E-mail: hadibotany@yahoo.com

Abstract

Salinity is one of the most important problems for the plant biodiversity. Salinity and water logging both cause great losses to the crops. The present research work was conducted to evaluate and compare the performance of three Pakistani cowpea varieties (Kulat-I, Kulat-II and Kulat-III) and one Australian variety (Ebony) under different NaCl salinity stresses. The experiment was conducted in pots under five NaCl salinity levels of 10 mM, 20 mM, 30mM, 40mM and 50 mM. The results showed that increasing salinity levels decreased the growth parameters of various varieties of cowpea. At 50 mM NaCl all the varieties exhibited extreme poor performance. Kulat-I performed well as compare to other varieties and displayed maximum % germination, plant height, leaves plant⁻¹, pods plant⁻¹, seeds pod⁻¹ and showed minimum days to germination and flowering at all levels of NaCl.

Key words: Cowpea varieties, NaCl salinity and growth performance.

Introduction

The Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* subsp. *unguiculata* (L.) Walp.) (Family Fabaceae) is commonly known as southern peas, black eyed pea, niebe, coope China pea, asparagus bean, yard long bean, frijol or lobia worldwide. It is a glabrescent scrambling annual herb reaching up to 80 cm or more in height. Cowpea is one of the most important food legume crops in the semi-arid tropics covering Asia, Africa, southern Europe and Central and South America. In Pakistan cowpea is introduced as a food plant having annual production of 553 tons from 257 hectares (Khushk & Laghari, 2007). The poor yield is attributed to unavailability of high yielding and stable genotypes along with appropriate advance agronomic practices. Being a minor crop in the country, it is usually cultivated for green pods and thus it does not reach to maturity and better yield. As a fodder it is a rich source of crude protein (Khan *et al.*, 2010).

Soil salinity is serious impediment for the growth of most crops. Silva *et al.*, (2003) stated that salinity levels adversely affected growth of cowpea. Amador *et al.*, (2006) while testing 25 genotypes of cowpea at different salinity levels and Amador & Dieguez (2007) reported that the weight of NaCl pre-treated seeds of cowpea decreased significantly at increased salinity. Filho (2008) observed that the lengths of the main root and shoot of cowpea decreased to 23 and 44 % respectively when treated with 100 mM NaCl. The effects of salinity on other plants has also been studied (Ibrar & Hussain 2003; Saqib *et al.*, 2004; Promila & Kumar 2005; Kaya *et al.*, 2007; Mahmood *et al.*, 2008 and Turan *et al.*, 2010). All they observed adverse effects on tested plants due to salinity.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was carried out in pots on three Pakistani varieties (Kulat-I, Kulat-II and Kulat-III) and one Australian variety (Ebony) of cowpea at Botanical Garden-Azakhel, University of Peshawar in year 2010-2011 to compare the local varieties with Australian variety (Ebony) at different salinity levels. Pots of 58 x 28 cm size were filled with equal amount of loamy soil and placed in Green house. Ten seeds from each of the varieties of cowpea were sown on June 24, 2010 at the depth of 5 cm in triplicate in the pots. The experiment was laid out in RCB design with three replications.

NaCl solutions of 10 mM, 20 mM, 30 mM, 40 mM and 50 mM concentrations were prepared. Pots were saturated once with the respective solution for the 1st time and thereafter watered with tape water as and when

needed. Control pots were watered with simple water. The data obtained were statistically analyzed using the procedure appropriate for RCB design upon obtaining significant F-test. The least significant difference (LSD) test was applied for the comparison of treatment means at 5% levels of probability.

Results and Discussion

Percentage germination

Table 1 indicates the data regarding germination percentage of cowpea. Analysis of data showed that different varieties (V) and NaCl concentrations (C) significantly affected germination. The V x C interaction was not significant. Control treatment had maximum (53.33 %) germination, while 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 Mm NaCl respectively provided 49.17, 46.67, 39.17, 33.33 and 30.83 % germination. The germination decreased significantly with increasing salinity levels. Kulat-I showed overall maximum germination (45.56 %) as compared to Ebony (45.0 %) and Kulat-II (41.67 %). Kulat-III had minimum (36.11 %) germination. Rajper & Sial (2002) and Gulzar *et al.*, (2003) reported that increasing salinity caused reduction in percentage seedling emergence of wheat and *Aeluropus lagopoides*. These findings are in line with our results. However, our results do not agree with Muhammad & Hussain (2010) who stated that there was no effect on % germination of tested plants.

Table 1. Percentage germination of four varieties of cowpea under different salinity levels of NaCl.

Varieties	Control	NaCl concentrations (mM)					Means
		10	20	30	40	50	
Kulat-I	56.67	53.33	53.33	43.33	36.67	30.00	45.56 a
Kulat-II	50.00	46.67	46.67	40.00	33.33	33.33	41.67 a
Kulat-III	46.67	43.33	43.33	33.33	26.67	23.33	36.11 b
Ebony	60.00	53.33	43.33	40.00	36.67	36.67	45.00 a
Means	53.33 a	49.17 a	46.67 a	39.17 bc	33.33 bc	30.83 c	

Mean of the same category followed by different letters are significantly different from one another.

LSD Value for varieties = 5.449 at α 0.05

LSD Value for NaCl levels = 6.673 at α 0.05

Days to germination

Table 2 shows that different varieties (V) and NaCl concentration (C) significantly affected the days to germination but V X C interaction was non significant. Germination took minimum (7.83) days in control condition. It was followed by treatments with 10 Mm (8.17), 20 Mm (9.58), 30 Mm (9.83), 40 Mm (10.67) and 50 Mm NaCl level prolonged the days (11.42) to germination. The minimum days (9.22) to germination were taken by Kulat-I, Kulat-III took 9.39 days, Kulat-II 9.78 days and Ebony 9.94 days. Germination delayed with enhanced salinity, i.e. Kulat-I took maximum days (7.33) to germination in control and 11 days at 50 Mm NaCl. Kulat-III had minimum days (8) to germination at control and 11 days at 50 mM NaCl. In Kulat-II minimum days (8) were recorded for control and maximum of 11.67 days at 50 Mm NaCl. For Kulat-IV the minimum and maximum days to germination were 8 and 12 respectively at control and 50 Mm NaCl. Kulat-I showed overall minimum days to germination (9.22 days) as compare to Kulat-III (9.39 days) and Kulat-II (9.78 days). Kulat-IV showed overall maximum days to germination (9.94 days cm). Muhammad & Hussain (2010) and Ghaloo *et al.*, (2011) reported that increase in NaCl concentrations increased the days to germination and thus agree with present findings. This may be due to the reason that plumule and radical growths decreases at high levels of salinity. Similar results were also obtained by Amador *et al.*, (2006) and Amador & Dieguez (2007) for other varieties of Cowpea under saline conditions. The findings also agree with those of Mahmood *et al.*, (2008) who observed poor performance *Sesbania* under saline conditions.

Table 2. Days to germination of four varieties of cowpea under different levels of NaCl salinity

Varieties	Control	NaCl concentrations (mM)					Means
		10	20	30	40	50	
Kulat-I	7.33	7.33	9.33	9.67	10.67	11.00	9.22 c
Kulat-II	8.00	8.33	9.33	10.00	11.33	11.67	9.78 ab
Kulat-III	8.00	8.33	9.67	9.67	9.67	11.00	9.39 bc
Ebony	8.00	8.67	10.00	10.00	11.00	12.00	9.94 a
Means	7.83 d	8.17 d	9.58 c	9.83 c	10.67	11.42 a	

Mean of the same category followed by different letters are significantly different from one another.

LSD Value for varieties = 0.482 at α 0.05

LSD Value for NaCl levels = 0.5903 at α 0.05

Plant height

Different varieties (V), NaCl concentration (C) and V x C interactions all had significantly affected the plant height (Table 3). Control had the maximum (139.20) plant height followed respectively by plants in 10 Mm (127.12), 20 Mm (97.73), 30 Mm (90.07), 40 Mm (86.78) and 50 Mm NaCl (82.35) treatments. Plants showed linear decrease in height with increasing salt concentration. Maximum plant height for Kulat-I was at control (171.67) that gradually decreased to minimum (86.20) at 50 mM NaCl. Kulat-II with maximum height at control (144.67 cm) linearly reached to minimum (80.37) at 40 mM NaCl. Kulat-III had maximum height at control (129.87) and minimum (78.77) at 40 mM. Ebony displayed maximum height (110.73) at 10 mM and declined to minimum (76.0) at 50 mM NaCl. The overall maximum height (120) was displayed by Kulat-I as compare to Kulat-II (102.28), Kulat-III (97.91) and Ebony (95.27). Our findings are supported by Mahmood *et al.*, (2009) who reported linearly reduction in the plant height in rice with increasing NaCl salinity. The reason behind this may be that under salinity, the osmotic pressure in soil solution exceeds the osmotic pressure in plants cells due to the presence of higher concentrations of salts, and thus reduces the ability of plants to take up water and minerals.

Table 3. Plant height (cm) of four varieties of cowpea under different levels of NaCl salinity.

Varieties	Control	NaCl concentrations (mM)					Means
		10	20	30	40	50	
Kulat-I	171.67	153.37	108.77	103.43	96.70	86.20	120 a
Kulat-II	144.67	117.33	100.33	84.87	80.37	86.20	102.28 b
Kulat-III	129.87	120.40	91.20	86.30	78.77	80.90	97.91 bc
Ebony	110.73	117.40	90.60	85.70	91.20	76.00	95.27 c
Means	139.20 a	127.12 b	97.73 c	90.07 d	86.78 de	82.35 e	

Mean of the same category followed by different letters are significantly different from one another.

LSD Value for varieties = 5.331 at α 0.05

LSD Value for NaCl levels = 6.529 at α 0.05

LSD Value for V x C Interaction = 13.06 at α 0.05

Number of leaves plant⁻¹

Number of leaves plant⁻¹ was significantly affected by different varieties (V) and NaCl concentration (C) with insignificant V x C interaction (Table 4). Plant grown under control condition had maximum leaves plant⁻¹ (59.25) followed by 10 Mm (56.83), 20 Mm (45.83), 30 Mm (36.67), 40 Mm (35.58) and 50 Mm NaCl (33.33) treatments. Increasing salinity level gradually decreased the number of leaves plant⁻¹ from maximum (69.0) at control to minimum (33.67) at 50 mM NaCl for Kulat-I. Kulat-II with maximum leaves plant⁻¹ at control (57.33) gradually reached to minimum (33.0) at 50 mM NaCl. Ebony provided maximum leaves plant⁻¹ at control (56.0) and minimum at 50 mM NaCl (34.67). Kulat-III had maximum leaves plant⁻¹ (54.67) at control that gradually declined to minimum (32.0) at 50 mM NaCl. The overall maximum leaves plant⁻¹ (47.94) were present in Kulat-I compared to Kulat-II (43.89), Kulat-III (43.50) and Ebony (43.0). Our findings are an agreement with those of Silva *et al.*, (2003) and Amador & Dieguez

(2007) who found that salinity induced reduction in number of leaves. Pettigrew (2008) reported that the deficiency of potassium under saline condition might cause reduction in number and size of leaves.

Table 4. Number of leaves plant⁻¹ of four varieties of cowpea under different levels of NaCl.

Varieties	Control	NaCl concentrations (mM)					Means
		10	20	30	40	50	
Kulat-I	69.00	64.67	46.33	37.00	37.00	33.67	47.94 a
Kulat-II	57.33	53.67	48.00	35.67	35.67	33.00	43.89 b
Kulat-III	54.67	56.33	45.33	38.00	34.67	32.00	43.50 b
Ebony	56.00	52.67	43.67	36.00	35.00	34.67	43.00 b
Means	59.25 a	56.83 a	45.83 b	36.67 c	35.58 cd	33.33 d	

Mean of the same category followed by different letters are significantly different from one another.

LSD Value for Factor (A) = 2.038 at α 0.05

LSD Value for Factor (B) = 2.503 at α 0.05

Days to flowering

Data indicated that different varieties (V) and NaCl levels (C) significantly affected the days to flowering with insignificant V x C interaction (Table 5). Days to flowering were minimum at control (54.08) that increased gradually with increasing salinity i.e. 10 Mm NaCl (55.75), 20 Mm NaCl (61.50), 30 Mm NaCl (63.17), 40 Mm NaCl (63.04) and 50 Mm NaCl (64.67). Days to flowering increased with increasing salinity, i.e. Kulat-I took minimum days to flowering at control (49.67) and maximum (62.0) at 50 mM NaCl. Kulat-II provided flowers at minimum days in control (53.33) which increased gradually to maximum (63.0) at 50 mM NaCl. Ebony took minimum days to flowering at control (56.0) and maximum at 50 mM NaCl (67.0). Kulat-III had minimum days to flowering (56.0) at control and increased to (66.67) at 50 mM NaCl. Kulat-I had overall minimum days to flowering (58.27) as compare to Kulat-II (59.83), Kulat-III (60.61) and Ebony (62.78). Amador & Dieguez (2007) are agreed with those of our findings that increase in salinity levels delayed the flowering. It may be due to fact that high salinity increased the duration for vegetative and reproduction growth due to salt stress and high osmotic pressure of salts in the cells of plants.

Table 5. Number of days to flowering of four varieties of cowpea under different concentrations of NaCl salinity.

Varieties	Control	NaCl concentrations (mM)					Means
		10	20	30	40	50	
Kulat-I	49.67	52.33	61.67	63.00	61.00	62.00	58.27 c
Kulat-II	53.33	54.00	61.00	65.00	62.67	63.00	59.83 b
Kulat-III	57.33	58.00	60.67	59.00	62.00	66.67	60.61 b
Ebony	56.00	58.67	62.67	65.67	66.67	67.00	62.78 a
Means	54.08 c	55.75 c	61.50 b	63.17 ab	63.03 a	64.67	

Mean of the same category followed by different letters are significantly different from one another.

LSD Value for Factor (A) = 1.47 at α 0.05

LSD Value for Factor (B) = 1.801 at α 0.05

Number of pods plant⁻¹

Table 6 showed that different varieties (V) and NaCl salinity (C) both have significantly affected the number of pods plant⁻¹ with insignificant V x C interaction. At 10 Mm NaCl treatment maximum (10.0) pods plant⁻¹ were achieved that decreased gradually from 9.83 in control to 8.75 (20 Mm), 7.33 (30 Mm), 6.42 (40 Mm) and 6.08 in 50 Mm NaCl. The data indicated that the number decreased linearly with increasing salinity. In Kulat-I maximum (11.67) and minimum (7.0) pods plant⁻¹ were obtained respectively at control and 50 mM NaCl. Kulat-II had maximum and minimum pods at 10 mM (10.67) and at 50 mM NaCl (6.33) respectively. Ebony produced maximum pods plant⁻¹ at control (9.33) that declined to minimum (5.0) at 50 mM NaCl. For Kulat-III the maximum pods (9.67) were obtained at 10 mM and

minimum (6.0) at 50 mM NaCl. The overall maximum pods plant⁻¹ (8.89) was yielded by Kulat-I compare to other tested varieties. Ahmad (2009) found in mungbean genotype that salt stress was more severe at vegetative, flowering and seed filling stages compare to seed development stage. This agrees with our results as in the present case gradual increase in salinity levels linearly reduced the number of pods due delayed and reduced flowering.

Table 6. Number of pods plants⁻¹ of four varieties of cowpea under different levels of NaCl salinity.

Varieties	Control	NaCl concentrations (mM)					Means
		10	20	30	40	50	
Kulat-I	11.67	10.33	9.33	8.00	7.00	7.00	8.89 a
Kulat-II	9.67	10.67	9.33	7.33	7.00	6.33	8.39 b
Kulat-III	8.67	9.67	8.33	6.67	5.67	6.00	7.50 c
Ebony	9.33	9.33	8.00	7.33	6.00	5.00	7.50 c
Means	9.83 a	10.00 a	8.75 b	7.33 c	6.42 d	6.08 d	

Mean of the same category followed by different letters are significantly different from one another.

LSD Value for Factor (A) = 0.4725 at α 0.05

LSD Value for Factor (B) = 0.5787 at α 0.05

Number of seeds pod⁻¹

Data regarding number of seeds pod⁻¹ indicates that different varieties (V) and increasing NaCl levels (C) had significant effects with insignificant V x C interaction (Table 7). Control had maximum seeds pod⁻¹ (11.0), which decreased with increasing salinity as at 10 and 20 mM (9.33), 30 Mm (8.33), 40 Mm (6.67) and 50 Mm NaCl (6.0). In Kulat-I maximum seeds pod⁻¹ were produced at control (11.0) and minimum (6.0) at 50 mM NaCl. Kulat-II had maximum (10.0) and minimum (6.0) seeds pod⁻¹ respectively at control and 50 mM NaCl. Kulat-III provided maximum seeds pod⁻¹ at control (9.33) and minimum at 50 mM NaCl (5.33). Ebony at 10 mM NaCl and 50 mM NaCl gave maximum (9.33) and maximum (5.67) seeds pod⁻¹ respectively. The overall maximum number of seeds pod⁻¹ (8.44) was yielded by Kulat-I, which was followed by Ebony (7.83), Kulat-II (7.78) and Kulat-III (7.39). Our results agree with those of Ahmad (2009) who also reported reduced flowers, pods and seeds under salinity stress. Gradual increase in salinity levels not only linearly reduced the number of pods but also reduced the number of seeds.

Table 7. Means table for the no. of seeds plant⁻¹ of four varieties of cowpea under different concentrations of NaCl.

Varieties	Control	NaCl concentrations (mM)					Means
		10	20	30	40	50	
Kulat-I	11.00	9.33	9.33	8.33	6.67	6.00	8.44 a
Kulat-II	10.00	8.33	8.00	8.00	6.67	5.67	7.78 b
Kulat-III	9.33	7.67	8.00	7.00	7.00	5.33	7.39 b
Ebony	9.33	9.33	9.33	7.00	6.33	5.67	7.83 b
Means	9.92 a	8.67 b	8.67 b	7.58 c	6.67 d	5.67 e	

Mean of the same category followed by different letters are significantly different from one another.

LSD Value for Factor (A) = 0.6057 at α 0.05

LSD Value for Factor (B) = 0.7419 at α 0.05

The local varieties gave better result as compare to Australian variety as different salinity levels. The present findings suggested that various tested varieties of cowpea might be growing on moderately saline soils especially for fodder purpose. Since this is a legume crop, it will improve the soil condition, fertility and add organic matter to soil compiled with suitable agronomic practices that might improve the soil for other subsequent cultivations. Further study is needed to see the biochemical changes that might have occurred due to salinity.

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